
Heat Wave in Classrooms: How Hot Temperatures Affect Student Learning

CHARAGIN A. GUADALQUIBER

Teacher III

Calolot Elementary School

Zamboanga del Sur, Region IX, Philippines

The intense heat is a frequent difficulty for both students and teachers in our country. The hot temperatures, particularly in the summer months, make it challenging to learn in the classroom. The heat doesn't only cause discomfort for students; it greatly affects their capacity to concentrate, comprehend, and remember information.

When the classroom is as hot as an oven, students find it difficult to focus. The brain finds it challenging to operate effectively in high temperatures, leading to difficulty in focusing on lessons. Instead of paying attention to the teacher, students tend to be distracted by the heat, often trying to cool off by fanning themselves or wiping away sweat. This ongoing discomfort drains their mental energy that could have been utilized for learning and grasping new ideas.

The students' physical well-being is also impacted by the heat. Dehydration increases the likelihood of fatigue setting in sooner. If students are not comfortable physically, they are less likely to engage actively in class discussions or activities. They could also feel drowsy or lethargic, which can make it difficult to follow along with the instruction. This indicates that even the most engaging topics can become boring and difficult to understand in extreme heat.

Furthermore, the situation is made worse by the inadequate ventilation in numerous classrooms. Lack of sufficient fans or air conditioning causes the air to become stale and motionless. This not only increases the temperature in the room but also makes it more difficult to inhale. A poorly ventilated room may lead to headaches and drowsiness, reducing students' capacity to learn effectively.

Teachers are also affected by the heat. If teachers feel uneasy, it may impact the quality of their teaching. They could hurry through lessons to finish quickly, or they may not be as engaging or enthusiastic as possible. This impacts the learning experience in general, as students notice their teacher's unease and lack of involvement.

To address these problems, schools must implement measures to establish a more conducive learning atmosphere. This might involve adding additional fans, making sure that classrooms have good ventilation, or potentially changing school schedules to avoid the hottest part of the day. Basic actions such as these can have a significant impact on maintaining students' concentration and drive.

To sum up, the high temperatures in the Philippines present a major obstacle to student education. Schools and authorities must acknowledge this problem and take steps to guarantee that learning environments stay conducive even in the warmest months. By tackling

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.286-289 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

the influence of heat on learning, we can support students in reaching their maximum capabilities despite the hurdles posed by the climate.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12590393

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.